

Supplementary Figure S2. Phylogram as inferred from the concatenated 14 mitochondrial and three nuclear ribosomal genes under the maximum likelihood criterion (new sequences in bold). SH-aLRT and ultrafast bootstrap (UFBoot) support values are shown at the top and below each branch, respectively. Abbreviations: Afrotropical (AFR), Australian (AUS), Neotropical (NEO), Oriental (ORI), Palearctic (PAL), Panamanian (PAN), Saharo-Arabian (SAH), and Sino-Japanese (SIN).

